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Glycolate production by a *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* mutant lacking carbon-concentrating mechanism

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Highlights

- *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* serves as a model organism for photosynthesis research.
- *C. reinhardtii* *cia5* mutant lacks a functional carbon-concentrating mechanism.
- Metabolic profiles of *cia5* mutant were changed as compared to its parental strain.
- The *cia5* mutant produced substantial amounts of glycolate at the autotrophic phase.
- This metabolomic approach is a tool for understanding the photosynthetic mechanisms.

Abstract

The green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* serves as a model organism for plant and photosynthesis research due to many commonalities in metabolism and the fast growth rate of *C. reinhardtii* accelerates experimental turn-around time. In addition, *C. reinhardtii* is a focus of research efforts in metabolic engineering and synthetic biology for the potential production of biofuels and value-added chemicals. Here, we report that the *C. reinhardtii* *cia5* mutant, which lacks a functional carbon-concentrating mechanism (CCM), can produce substantial amounts of glycolate, a high-value cosmetic ingredient, when the mutant is cultured under ambient air conditions. In order to reveal the metabolic basis of glycolate accumulation by the *cia5* mutant, we investigated the metabolomes of the *cia5* mutant and its parental strain CC-125 (WT) through the global metabolic profiling of intracellular and extracellular fractions using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry. We observed the intracellular and extracellular metabolic profiles of WT and *cia5* mutant were similar during the heterotrophic phase at 30 h. However, when the cells entered the autotrophic phase (i.e., 96 h and 120 h), both the intracellular and extracellular metabolic profiles of *cia5* mutant differed significantly when compared to WT. In the *cia5* mutant strain, a group of photorespiration pathway intermediates including glycolate, glyoxylate, glycine, and serine accumulated to significantly higher levels compared to WT. In the photorespiration pathway, glycolate is metabolized to glyoxylate and glycine leading to NH₃ and CO₂ generation during the mitochondrial conversion of glycine to serine. This result provides further evidence that the *cia5* mutation increased the photorespiration rate. Because the *cia5* mutant lacks a CCM, and *C. reinhardtii* might harbor an inefficient or incomplete photorespiration

pathway, glycolate may accumulate when the CCM is not functional. We envision that investigating photorespiration controls in *C. reinhardtii* provides tools for producers to use the *cia5* mutant to produce glycolate as well as platform to engineer alternative pathways for glycolate metabolism.

Keywords: *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*, glycolate, CIA5, photorespiration, carbon concentrating mechanism (CCM)

1. Introduction

In photosynthesis, ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (Rubisco) catalyzes the fixation of inorganic carbon (i.e., CO₂) to ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate (RuBP) and generates two molecules of 3-phosphoglycerate (**Fig. 1A**). Alternatively, its oxygenase mode, Rubisco fixes O₂ from the atmosphere to RuBP and generates one 3-carbon unit (i.e., 3-phosphoglycerate) and a 2-carbon unit (i.e., 2-phosphoglycolate) (**Fig. 1A**). While 3-phosphoglycerate can re-enter the photosynthetic cycle, 2-phosphoglycolate cannot and in addition 2-phosphoglycolate inhibits the activity of enzymes involved in the Calvin-Benson cycle (e.g., Deller et al., 2016). Photosynthetic eukaryotes have evolved a complicated and energy-consuming photorespiration pathway to detoxify and recycle glycolate to generate glycerate and evolve a CO₂ (**Fig. 1B**). The Rubisco functionality changes based on the nearby O₂ and CO₂ concentrations so that organisms that concentrate inorganic carbon near the site of Rubisco can increase the carboxylase rate at the expense of the oxygenase rate and thereby increase net photosynthesis and biomass production.

Badger observed the carbon concentrating mechanism (CCM) in the green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (Badger et al., 1980) and other CCMs exist in cyanobacteria and red/brown algae (as reviewed by Giordano et al., 2005). Briefly, the carbon concentrating mechanism includes enzymes that are transcriptionally induced in response to low environmental CO₂ concentrations and are essential in elevating inorganic carbon at the Rubisco catalytic site.

C. reinhardtii microalgae is an established model system to study eukaryotic mechanisms of photosynthesis and photorespiration (Rochaix, 2002). This microalga

has a short generation time ranging from 7.9 to 8.8 h depending on media supplementation (Kropat et al., 2011) and displays phenotypic traits quickly. The available *C. reinhardtii* reference genome (Merchant et al., 2007) enables a comparative investigation into the functions of photosynthetic gene mechanisms in higher plants (Blaby et al., 2014). The *CIA5* gene codes for a CIA5 transcription factor protein (Fukuzawa, 2001; Moroney, 1989). This CIA5 protein responds to higher or lower levels of CO₂ (Fang et al., 2012) and influences the expression of many CO₂-responsive genes. Xiang et al. reported that a healthy CIA5 gene could complement a *C. reinhardtii* mutated in the *CIA5* gene where CCM function had been lost and photosynthetic efficiency in the cells decreased (Xiang et al., 2001). Researchers have investigated the functions of the CIA5 protein and the far-reaching effects at the genome and transcriptome levels (Fang et al., 2012; Marek and Spalding, 1991; Xiang et al., 2001). However, the metabolic phenotype of the cell in response to a *CIA5* gene mutation in *C. reinhardtii* remains limited.

In this study, we investigated the metabolic characteristics of *C. reinhardtii* with a *CIA5* gene mutation. We used gas chromatography and mass spectrometry (GC/MS) to profile the intracellular and extracellular metabolites of a *C. reinhardtii* *cia5* mutant and wild type CC-125 (WT) in order to identify the metabolites in both the intracellular and extracellular fractions of the *cia5* mutant that accumulated compared to the WT. This study provides useful information to explain the effects of deleting a CCM-related gene on the metabolic phenotype of photosynthetic organisms such as green algae and plants.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Strains and culture conditions

We purchased *C. reinhardtii* CC-125 (WT) and CC-2702 (*cia5* mutant) strains from the Chlamydomonas Resource Center (<http://www.chlamycollection.org>) and cultivated the strains in 125-mL flasks of liquid Tris-Acetate-Phosphate (TAP) medium on a shaker platform set at 100 rpm (Gorman and Levine, 1965). Flasks were continuously illuminated at $65 \mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Li-COR model Li-189, sensor = Quantum (Q40180)) using cool-white fluorescent light (GE Ecolux w/ Starcoat 4100K 32W) at 25°C and 100 rpm. Cell growth was monitored by measuring the optical density at 750 nm (OD_{750}) using a Biomate 3S (Thermo Electron Corporation, Waltham, MA, US).

2.2. High-performance liquid chromatography

We monitored the acetate consumption and the glycolate production in the WT and *cia5* mutant strains using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with a refractive index detector and an H+ column (Rezex ROA-Organic Acid; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA). We set the column temperature and the refractive index detector to 50°C. We used 2.5 mM H₂SO₄ as a mobile phase and set the flow rate to 0.6 mL/min.

2.3. Preparation of the samples for metabolic profiling by GC/MS

For intracellular metabolite analysis, we used the methanol quenching method as previously described with a slight modification (Kim et al., 2013). Briefly, we collected cells during culture and twice washed the cells using ice-cold water. We quickly mixed

the washed cells and added 1 mL of a pre-chilled acetonitrile–water mixture (1:1, v/v) and 100 μ L of glass beads. Then, we vortexed the extraction mixture for 3 min to extract intracellular metabolites of WT and *cia5* mutant strains by disruption of the cell membrane and centrifuged the mixture at 16,100 $\times g$ for 3 min at 4°C. We took 0.8 mL of the supernatant containing the intracellular metabolites and dried the material in a speed vacuum concentrator for 6 h.

To analyze extracellular metabolites, we dried 20 μ L of the culture supernatant in the speed vacuum concentrator for 6 h.

2.4. Metabolite profiling by GC/MS

Before GC/MS analysis, we derivatized the extracted metabolites by methoxyamination and trimethylsilylation. The methoxyamination step began as we added 10 μ L of 40 mg/mL methoxyamine chloride in pyridine (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, US) to the samples and then incubated the samples for 90 min at 30°C, shaking at 200 rpm. Then, we added 45 μ L of *N*-methyl-*N*-trimethylsilyltrifluoroacetamide (MSTFA; Sigma-Aldrich) to the samples for trimethylsilylation and incubated for 30 min at 37°C and 200 rpm shaking. For the detection of small molecular weight compounds such as glycolate, we performed *tert*-butyldimethylsilylation instead of trimethylsilylation by adding 45 μ L of *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl-*N*-methyltrifluoroacetamide (MTBSTFA; Sigma-Aldrich) instead of MSTFA.

For GC/MS analysis, we applied the derivatized metabolite samples to an Agilent 7890A GC/5975C MSD system (Agilent Technologies, Wilmington, DE) equipped with an RTX-5Sil MS capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm, 0.25 μ m film

thickness; Restek, Bellefonte, PA) and an additional 10-m-long integrated guard column. We injected one microliter of the derivatized sample into the GC inlet in splitless mode. Initially, the oven temperature was set to 150°C for 1 min, after which the temperature increased to 330°C at 20°C/min, where it remained for 5 min after reaching 330°C. The system recorded the mass spectra in a scan range 85–500 m/z at electron impact of 70 eV, and the temperatures of the ion source and transfer line were 230°C and 280°C, respectively.

2.5. Metabolite data processing and statistical analyses

We preprocessed the raw data obtained from GC/MS analysis in an automated mass spectral deconvolution and identification system (AMDIS) software (Stein, 1999) for peak detection and deconvolution. Then, we uploaded the pre-processed data into SpectConnect (Styczynski et al., 2007) for peak alignment and for generation of the data matrix with Golm Metabolome Database (GMD) mass spectral reference library. We obtained the normalized abundance values for each metabolite by dividing peak intensity with dry cell weight. For multivariate statistical analysis and clustering analysis, such as principal component analysis (PCA) and hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA), we used Statistica (version 7.1; StatSoft, Palo Alto, CA) and MultiExperiment Viewer software (Howe et al., 2010), respectively.

3. Results

*3.1. Growth profiles of *C. reinhardtii* WT and *cia5* mutant*

We monitored cell growth, acetate consumption, and extracellular metabolite production by *C. reinhardtii* CC-125 (WT) and CC-2702 (*cia5* mutant) strains (**Fig. 2**). We added acetate (1.0 g/L) into the culture broth as a carbon source for both WT and *cia5* mutant strains. Growth profiles for both strains as measured by OD₇₅₀ were similar during the acetate-consuming phase (i.e., heterotrophic phase) (**Fig. 2A**). Intriguingly, after acetate depletion at approximately 72 h and the start of the autotrophic phase, the *cia5* mutant started to produce glycolate, the key metabolic substrate for the photorespiration pathway (**Fig. 2B**). Meanwhile, WT did not produce glycolate at all during the autotrophic phase (**Fig. 2B**). During the autotrophic phase, the OD₇₅₀ values decreased in the *cia5* mutant, whereas those obtained from WT increased slightly (**Fig. 2A**).

3.2. Analysis of the intracellular and extracellular metabolites of WT and *cia5* mutant

We investigated the metabolic basis that led the *cia5* mutant to accumulate glycolate by using a principal component analysis (PCA) of WT and *cia5* mutant metabolites obtained from GC/MS analysis data (**Fig. 3A and 3B**). In total, 54 intracellular metabolites and 24 extracellular metabolites belonging to amino acids, sugars, organic acids, fatty acids, phosphates, and nucleosides were identified in WT and *cia5* mutant (**Table S1 and S2**). Interestingly, two dimensional PCA results obtained from intracellular metabolites of WT and *cia5* mutant showed a clear separation between the two different growth phases, a heterotrophic phase and an autotrophic phase, and the two different strains, WT and *cia5* mutant, with an R^2X value of 0.535, which indicates goodness of fit of the PCA model (**Fig. 3A**). More specifically, PC1 majorly contributed to discriminate two different growth phases (i.e., a heterotrophic phase and an

autotrophic phase). Meanwhile, PC2 contributed to discriminate two different strains, WT and *cia5* mutant, during the autotrophic phase (**Fig. 3A**).

The PCA results of extracellular metabolites of WT and *cia5* mutant differed with those obtained from intracellular metabolites (**Fig. 3A and 3B**). Only the extracellular metabolite profiles obtained from *cia5* mutant during an autotrophic phase (i.e., CIA5_96 h and CIA5_120 h) were discriminated from the other conditions by PC1 (**Fig. 3B**). The metabolite profiles of *cia5* mutant during a heterotrophic phase (i.e., CIA5_30 h) or of WT during both a heterotrophic phase and an autotrophic phase (i.e., WT_30 h, WT_96 h, and WT_120 h) were not discriminated PCA analysis (**Fig. 3B**).

We listed the loading scores for the 54 intracellular and 24 extracellular metabolites on PC1 and PC2 in **Table S3 and S4**, respectively. Of the total metabolites identified in this study, we focused on the loading scores of the metabolites found in photorespiration, photosynthesis, and glycolysis pathways. In the intracellular PCA results, the metabolic intermediates of glycolysis such as 3-phosphoglycerate, pyruvate, and dihydroxyacetone phosphate made a positive contribution to PC1 (**Fig. 3A and Table S3**). Meanwhile, the metabolic intermediates involved in photorespiration pathway such as glycolate, glycine, and serine, made a positive contribution to PC2 (**Fig. 3A and Table S3**). However, in the extracellular PCA results, the metabolic intermediates of photorespiration pathway such as glutamate, glycine, and glycolate made a negative contribution to PC1 (**Fig. 3B and Table S4**).

3.3. Clustering analysis of the metabolites obtained from C. reinhardtii CC-125 and cia5 mutant

We selected 18 samples (two different strains × three different sampling time points × triplicates) from the identified intracellular and extracellular metabolites and subjected them to hierarchical clustering analysis (HCA) to identify possible differences in the intracellular and extracellular metabolite profiles of WT and *cia5* strain. Clustering of intracellular metabolites resulted in good separation based on the strains, WT and *cia5* mutant, and sampling time points (**Fig. 4A**). More specifically, intracellular metabolites obtained from heterotrophic phase and autotrophic phase separated regardless of the strain background (**Fig. 4A**). During the heterotrophic phase, pyruvate, 3-phosphoglycerate, and dihydroxyacetone phosphate accumulated at high levels in both WT and *cia5* mutant (**Fig. 4A**). However, we noticed most of the identified intracellular metabolites accumulated during the autotrophic phase in both strains. After entering the autotrophic phase at 96 h and 120 h, the metabolite profiles were clustered based on the types of strains, WT and *cia5* mutant (**Fig. 4A**). Also, in *cia5* mutant at 120 h, the abundances of the metabolites such as glucose, glucose 6-phosphate, malate, and fumarate, which are involved in the central carbon metabolism were significantly reduced compared to the results obtained from *cia5* mutant at 96 h (Fig. 4A). This is probably due to the cell death of *cia5* mutant caused by the continued low net photosynthetic activity in the autotrophic phase.

Meanwhile, extracellular metabolites clusters separated *cia5* mutant during autotrophic phase from other phases (**Fig. 4B**). During the autotrophic phase, the amino acids closely related to photorespiration pathway (i.e., serine, glycine, glutamate) and C2 compounds involved in the photorespiration pathway (i.e., glyoxylate and glycolate) were significantly accumulated in the *cia5* mutant culture (**Fig. 4B**).

3.4. Metabolomic changes related to photosynthesis

According to the PCA and HCA analyses described above, the metabolite profiles of the *C. reinhardtii* WT and the *cia5* mutant differed significantly in the abundances of metabolic intermediates of photosynthesis and photorespiration pathways (**Figs 3 and 4**). Among the metabolic intermediates of photosynthesis, 3-phosphoglycerate, generated via the reactions of ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate and CO₂ by Rubisco, were greater in WT at 96 h as compared to the WT at 120 h and the *cia5* mutant at 96 h and 120 h (**Fig. 5**). Glycerol 3-phosphate and glycerol 2-phosphate were abundant in WT at 96 h and 120 h as compared to *cia5* mutant at 96 h and 120 h (**Fig. 5**). Glycerol phosphates, glycerol 3-phosphate and glycerol 2-phosphate, are metabolic intermediates of the glycerolipid pathway, which is a branched pathway derived from glycolysis (Riekhof et al., 2005). Furthermore, the intensities of glucose and glucose 6-phosphate, the intermediates of upper glycolysis, were elevated in WT at 96 and 120 h and *cia5* at 96 h (**Fig. 5**).

3.5. Metabolomic changes related to photorespiration

With regard to the photorespiration pathway, the *cia5* mutant accumulated significant amounts of glycolate both intracellularly and extracellularly (**Fig. 6A and B**). Crucial amino acids involved in the photorespiration pathway — serine, glutamate, and glycine — increased in the *cia5* mutant at 96 and 120 h (**Fig. 6A**). Among those, we also observed extracellular accumulation of glutamate and glycine (**Fig. 6B**). Most notably,

the C2 compound glyoxylate, which is generated from glycolate, accumulated extracellularly in *cia5* mutant cultures at 96 h and 120 h (**Fig. 6B**).

3.6. Production of glycolate by *cia5* mutant strain

Based on the results obtained from the intracellular and extracellular metabolic profiling of WT and *cia5* mutant, we confirmed the substantial accumulation of glycolate by the *cia5* mutant. Glycolate is the simplest α -hydroxy acid and is used as an exfoliant or buffering agent by improving skin texture in cosmetics and personal care products (Rendon et al., 2008). Chemists also use glycolate to synthesize polymers with excellent gas barrier properties by using glycolate alone or with other acid units, including L-lactate (Fredenberg et al., 2011). Thus, we tried to cultivate the *cia5* mutant to produce glycolate. During the autotrophic growth, only the *cia5* mutant produced glycolate, whereas WT did not produce glycolate (**Fig. 7**). After 140 h, the *cia5* mutant produced 0.3 g/L of glycolate (**Fig. 7**).

4. Discussion

The *CIA5* gene influences CCM function (Fang et al., 2012; Giordano et al., 2005; Xiang et al., 2001), however, there are limited descriptions of the phenotypic changes in response to the mutation of the *CIA5* gene in *C. reinhardtii*. In this study, we observed the phenotypic changes by a *cia5* mutant leading to accumulation of C2 compounds (i.e., glycolate and glyoxylate) using global metabolic profiling of intracellular and extracellular metabolites of the *cia5* mutant and WT.

During the heterotrophic phase, global metabolic profiling obtained from the intracellular and extracellular metabolites of *C. reinhardtii* WT and *cia5* mutant were similar (**Figs. 3A and 3B**). This implies that *CIA5* gene mutation resulting in a malfunctioning CCM did not change the phenotypes and metabolic fluxes during the heterotrophic phase. The genes related to CCM, including *CIA5*, are downregulated during the heterotrophic phase based on the presence of an organic carbon source (e.g., acetic acid) (Heifetz et al., 2000).

However, when the cells depleted their organic carbon supply at the onset of the autotrophic phase, the metabolite profiles of *C. reinhardtii* WT and *cia5* mutant were significantly changed (**Figs. 3A and 3B**). In the autotrophic phase, green algae *Chlamydomonas* species synthesize organic carbon through photosynthesis (Hanikenne, 2003). The *CIA5* gene, a CCM transcriptional regulator, plays a crucial role for CCM regulation to increase CO₂ availability to Rubisco (Fang et al., 2012; Xiang et al., 2001). Based on the multivariate statistical analyses using PCA and HCA, we observed the primary metabolite profiles changes in the intermediates associated with photorespiration. The primary function of the photorespiration pathway is to generate a C₃ compound (e.g., 3-phosphoglycerate) from two C₂ compound (e.g., phosphoglycolate) (Dellero et al., 2016) and the concomitant evolution of a CO₂ molecule. In this study, we found that the *cia5* mutant produces substantial amounts of glycolate during the autotrophic growth phase with a portion of it released extracellularly. This means that although green algae *Chlamydomonas* species have a photorespiration pathway to generate C₃ compounds for feeding the central metabolic pathway such as glycolysis, that there is leakage of glycolate from the photorespiratory

pathway making it more energetically inefficient than it already is. Therefore, to improve the photorespiration pathway efficiency in green algae *Chlamydomonas* species, the introduction of a highly active alternative glycolate metabolism pathway is feasible (South et al., 2019). On the other hand, since the cosmetic industry uses glycolate as an ingredient, the *cia5* mutant strain has a potential role as a glycolate production factory driven by light energy.

In conclusion, we discovered that the production of glycolate by *cia5* mutant is substantial, and it offers a resource for production of this high-value cosmetic ingredient. The metabolite profiling results revealed the accumulation of C2 compounds, including glycolate and glyoxylate, and we presume production was a consequence of an inefficient photosynthetic mechanism caused by a dysfunctional CCM in the *cia5* mutant and the inefficient photorespiration pathway requiring multiple reactions and energy. This study provides useful information to explain the effects of mutating CCM-related genes on the metabolic phenotype of photosynthetic organisms such as green algae and plants. Therefore, we demonstrated use of a metabolomic approach to understand, modify, or enhance the photosynthetic mechanisms.

Authors' contributions

YSJ conceived the project. EJY, GCZ, and CA designed the experiments. GCZ and CA performed cultivation of *C. reinhardtii*. EJY and SL performed metabolomic analysis and data interpretation. EJY, CA, DRO and YSJ wrote the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors report no declarations of interest.

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Figure Captions

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram illustrating the photosynthetic and photorespiratory pathways. The schematic diagram is adapted from the previous literature (Kroth et al., 2008).

Fig. 2. Comparison of the fermentation profiles of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* WT (WT) and *cia5* mutant (CIA5) strains. (A) Cell growth and (B) acetate consumption and glycolate production of WT and CIA5.

Fig. 3. The two-dimensional PCA scatter plots generated from (A) the 54 intracellular metabolites and (B) the 24 extracellular metabolites of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* WT (WT) and *cia5* mutant (CIA5) strains. The labels in the PCA scatter plot represent the two different strains (i.e., WT and CIA5) with three different sampling time points (i.e., 30 h, 96 h, and 120 h). All experiments were performed in triplicate.

Fig. 4. The heat maps of (A) the 54 intracellular metabolites and (B) the 24 extracellular metabolites of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* WT (WT) and *cia5* mutant (CIA5) strains. The x-axis labels represent the two different strains (i.e., WT and CIA5) with three different sampling time points (i.e., 30 h, 96 h, and 120 h). The y-axis labels represent (A) the 54 intracellular metabolites and (C) the 24 extracellular metabolites identified in this study. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

Fig. 5. The normalized abundance levels of the intracellular metabolites of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* WT (WT) and *cia5* mutant (CIA5) strains related to

photosynthesis and glycolysis during the autotrophic phase (i.e., 96 h and 120 h) are shown in the box-whisker plots.

Fig. 6. The normalized abundance levels of (A) the intracellular and (B) extracellular metabolites of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* WT (WT) and *cia5* mutant (CIA5) strains related to photorespiration pathway during the autotrophic phase (i.e., 96 h and 120 h) are shown in the box-whisker plots.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the production of glycolate by *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* WT (WT) and *cia5* mutant (CIA5) strains.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4A

Fig. 4B

Fig. 5

Intracellular

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Supplementary information

Glycolate production by a *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* mutant lacking carbon-concentrating mechanism

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Table S1. A total of 54 intracellular metabolites of WT and *cia5* mutant strains, as identified by GC-MS analysis

Amino acids (17)

Alanine
Arginine
Aspartate
Glutamate
Glycine
Isoleucine
Leucine
Lysine
Norleucine

Ornithine
Phenylalanine
Proline
Serine
Threonine
Tryptophan
Tyrosine
Valine

Sugars (3)

Glucose
Myo-inositol

Xylose

Phosphates (8)

Adenosine 5-monophosphate
Dihydroxyacetone phosphate
Glucose 6-phosphate
Glycerol 2-phosphate

Glycerol 3-phosphate
Myo-inositol 1-phosphate
Phosphate
Pyrophosphate

Fatty acids (5)

2-Hexadecenoic acid
9,12-Octadecadienoic acid
Hexadecanoic acid

Octadecanoic acid
Octadecatrienoic acid

Organic acids (9)

1-Pyrroline-3-hydroxy-5-carboxylate
3-Phosphoglycerate
Benzoate
Fumarate

Malate
Nicotinic acid
Pyruvate
Tocopherol

Glycolate

Nucleosides (7)

Adenine

Guanosine

Adenosine

Uracil

Cytosine

Uridine

Guanine

Others (5)

1-Heneicosanol

Phytol

Borate

Putrescine

Ethanolamine

Table S2. A total of 24 extracellular metabolites of WT and *cia5* mutant strains, as identified by GC-MS analysis

Amino acids (8)

Alanine

Proline

Glutamate

Serine

Glycine

Threonine

Norleucine

Valine

Sugars (1)

Myo-inositol

Phosphates (1)

Phosphate

Fatty acids (3)

Hexadecanoic acid

Sphingosine

Octadecanoic acid

Organic acids (7)

Benzoate

Malate

Fumarate

Nicotinic acid

Glycolate

Pyruvate

Glyoxylate

Nucleosides (1)

Uracil

Others (3)

Borate

Putrescine

Ethanolamine

Table S3. A total of 54 intracellular metabolites with loadings on PC1 and PC2, as determined by PCA

PC1		PC2	
Metabolite	Loading	Metabolite	Loading
Threonine	-0.9627	Glycerol 3-phosphate	-0.8
Xylose	-0.9495	Uridine	-0.8
Guanine	-0.9452	Putrescine	-0.6
Tyrosine	-0.9441	Arginine	-0.6
Ethanolamine	-0.9268	Adenosine	-0.6
Phenylalanine	-0.9267	Cytosine	-0.5
Lysine	-0.9206	3-Phosphoglycerate	-0.5
Adenine	-0.9181	Mannose 6-phosphate	-0.5
Octadecatrienoic acid	-0.9021	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid	-0.5
Hexadecanoic acid	-0.8978	Fumarate	-0.4
Glycerol-2-phosphate	-0.8611	Malate	-0.4
Benzoate	-0.8602	Galactose	-0.4
Phosphate	-0.8588	Phosphate	-0.4
Pyrophosphate	-0.8446	Uracil	-0.3
Galactose	-0.8438	Glycerol 2-phosphate	-0.3
Guanosine	-0.8274	2-Hexadecenoic acid	-0.3
Uracil	-0.8192	Ornithine	-0.3
Myo-inositol-1-phosphate	-0.8157	Alanine	-0.3
9,12-Octadecadienoic acid	-0.8053	Dihydroxyacetone phosphate	-0.2
2-Hexadecenoic acid	-0.7919	Pyruvate	-0.2
Glutamate	-0.7777	Adenosine-5-monophosphate	-0.2
Glycine	-0.7733	Octadecatrienoic acid	-0.2
Malate	-0.7669	Ethanolamine	-0.1
Valine	-0.7637	Proline	-0.1
Fumarate	-0.7634	Adenine	-0.1
Myo-inositol	-0.7472	Pyrophosphate	-0.1
Mannose-6-phosphate	-0.7353	Threonine	-0.1

Adenosine-	-0.7250	Isoleucine	-0.1
Octadecanoic acid	-0.7008	Xylose	-0.0
Serine	-0.6760	Glutamate	-0.0
Leucine	-0.6729	Octadecanoic acid	0.0
1-Heneicosanol	-0.6636	1-Pyrroline-3-hydroxy-5-carboxylate	0.1
Putrescine	-0.6335	Leucine	0.1
Alanine	-0.6247	Guanine	0.1
Phytol	-0.6084	Benzoate	0.1
Nicotinic acid	-0.5770	Norleucine	0.1
Isoleucine	-0.5333	Valine	0.2
Norleucine	-0.5105	Phenylalanine	0.2
Aspartate	-0.5003	Tyrosine	0.2
Uridine	-0.4793	Hexadecanoic acid	0.2
Tocopherol	-0.4741	Lysine	0.2
Cytosine	-0.4042	Nicotinic acid	0.2
Tryptophan	-0.4027	Tocopherol	0.3
Adenosine-5-monophosphate	-0.3513	Myo-inositol-1-phosphate	0.3
Proline	-0.2848	Guanosine	0.4
Glycolate	-0.2755	Phytol	0.4
Glycerol-3-phosphate	-0.2235	Borate	0.4
1-Pyrroline-3-hydroxy-5-carboxylate	0.0210	Myo-inositol	0.4
Borate	0.1296	Aspartate	0.5
Arginine	0.2927	Serine	0.5
Ornithine	0.3887	Tryptophan	0.5
3-Phosphoglycerate	0.6011	Glycine	0.5
Pyruvate	0.6293	1-Heneicosanol	0.5
Dihydroxyacetone phosphate	0.7000	Glycolate	0.7

Table S4. A total of 24 extracellular metabolites with loadings on PC1 and PC2, as determined by PCA

PC1		PC2	
Metabolite	Loading	Metabolite	Loading
Glutamate	-0.9711	Phosphate	-0.8
Glycine	-0.9504	Sphingosine	-0.7
Glycolate	-0.9419	Benzoate	-0.7
Putrescine	-0.9270	Hexadecanoic acid	-0.6
Glyoxylate	-0.9194	Octadecanoic acid	-0.5
Myo-inositol	-0.9182	Alanine	-0.4
Threonine	-0.8201	Malate	-0.2
Proline	-0.7829	Uracil	-0.2
Malate	-0.7737	Glyoxylate	-0.2
Fumarate	-0.7363	Serine	-0.2
Serine	-0.6884	Nicotinic acid	-0.1
Ethanolamine	-0.6683	Threonine	-0.1
Norleucine	-0.3762	Glutamate	-0.0
Valine	-0.3749	Putrescine	-0.0
Alanine	-0.3541	Glycolate	-0.0
Pyruvate	-0.0244	Glycine	-0.0
Nicotinic acid	0.0579	Proline	-0.0
Hexadecanoic acid	0.0812	Fumarate	-0.0
Borate	0.1324	Valine	0.0
Octadecanoic acid	0.1898	Myo-inositol	0.0
Benzoate	0.2260	Norleucine	0.1
Uracil	0.3274	Ethanolamine	0.2
Phosphate	0.3443	Pyruvate	0.5
Sphingosine	0.4207	Borate	0.6

